

AVALANCHE

Abdurakhmanova Sayyorakhon Ruzaliyevna,

*Teacher Fergana Region Emergency Situations
Department Life Safety Training Center, Uzbekistan*

Annotation: this article covers the types of rams, their classifications and what to do if they are left in the whirlpool of landslides, how to protect from them, as an unfortunate coincidence.

Key words: landslide, self - sufficiency, landslide, snow, volume, earthquakes.

An avalanche is a significant volume of snow falling or sliding down steep mountain slopes at a speed of about 20-30 m/s. An avalanche is often accompanied by a side effect in the form of an air pre-avalanche wave, which produces the greatest destruction.

An avalanche, as a natural phenomenon, can pose considerable danger, causing human casualties (in particular, among climbers, lovers of skiing and snowboarding) and causing significant damage to material property. Avalanches are dangerous for people because of their mass (sometimes reaching several hundred tons), which leads to death from shock as a result of broken bones, as well as weak or no air permeability at all, which is why the victim dies from lack of oxygen (asphyxia). In addition, an avalanche can carry a person off a slope, as a result of which he can crash to death when falling from it. If the snow that has fallen from the avalanche that covered the victim gets into the victim's respiratory organs (mouth, nose, or even further), he will die due to the inability to breathe. Additionally, the weak sound conductivity of the snow (due to the fact that it is soft) prevents an avalanche victim from getting free, and as a result, rescuers may not hear the screams of a person from under the avalanche.

Snow avalanches, to one degree or another, are common in all mountainous regions of the Russian Federation and in most mountainous regions of the world.

The total area of avalanche - prone territories in Russia reaches 3077,800 km², which is up to 18% of the total area of the country. In addition to them, another 829.4 thousand km² are classified as potentially avalanche - prone. It is worth noting that avalanche-prone regions on Earth have a total area of 9253 thousand km², which corresponds to about 7% of the land.

In winter, avalanches are the main natural danger of the mountains. Sometimes avalanches have catastrophic consequences. So, in February 1999, an avalanche weighing 170 thousand tons completely destroyed the village of Galtur in Austria, causing the death of 30 people, and in early March 2012, a series of avalanches in Afghanistan destroyed residential buildings, causing the death of at least 100 people. Some years are especially rich in avalanches when they descend in many places, for example, the 1950 - 1951 season, dubbed the Winter of Horror.

Snow, falling in the form of precipitation, is held on the slope due to the friction force. Its value depends on the humidity of the snow, the steepness of the slope. An avalanche occurs at the moment when the pressure force of the snow mass begins to exceed the friction force.

Slopes with a steepness of 25-45° are the most favorable for avalanche formation, but avalanches are known to descend from slopes with a steepness of 15-18°. At the same time, avalanches sometimes descend from very gentle slopes - 10-15°. On slopes steeper than 50°, snow cannot accumulate in large quantities and rolls down in small doses as it arrives, however, an avalanche-safe slope is considered to be 15° or steeper than 60°.

It is believed that a slope of 15° with a snow depth of 15 cm can be avalanche - prone if a number of conditions are met, for example, the initial thaw and strong spring solar radiation, as a result of which the snow melted, then a sudden severe frost, which formed an icy slope, and then a heavy snowfall, powdered the icy horizon. The descent from the slope of the accumulated snow mass is usually provoked by climatic reasons: a sharp change in weather (including changes in atmospheric pressure, humidity), rains, heavy snowfall, as well as mechanical effects on the snow mass, including the impact of rock falls, earthquakes, etc.

Sometimes, due to the established relative equilibrium between the acting friction force and the pressure force, an avalanche can be initiated by a slight push (for example, the sound of a gunshot, wind from helicopter blades or pressure on the snow of one person - a skier, snowboarder). Avalanche barriers on the Heferspitz mountain in Vorarlberg (western Austria) The volume of snow in an avalanche can reach up to several million cubic meters. However, even avalanches with a volume of about 5 m³ can be life-threatening.

There are several classifications of avalanches, for example:

- ✓ according to the form of the beginning of the avalanche movement;
- ✓ by the nature of the avalanche movement;
- ✓ by volume;
- ✓ according to the relief of the avalanche collection and the path of the avalanche (wasp, tray avalanche, jumping avalanche);
- ✓ according to the consistency of snow (dry, wet and wet avalanches).

At the same time, according to the form of the beginning of the avalanche movement, they are divided into:

- ✓ avalanches from the line (“snow boards”, snow - ice, ice);
- ✓ avalanches from the point (dry and wet).

References:

1. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On ensuring seismic safety of the population and territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan” No. ZRU-713 dated 13.09.2021.
 2. Decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the classification of emergency situations of a man-made, natural and environmental nature” No. 455 dated 10/27/1998.
 3. “Tutorial on predicting the consequences of an earthquake” Institute of Civil Protection of the Ministry of Emergency Situations of the Republic of Uzbekistan. 2007
 4. “Tutorial on the protection of the population and territories from emergency situations” Institute of Civil Protection of the Ministry of Emergency Situations of the Republic of Uzbekistan. 2018
- Отуотер М. Охотники за лавинами = The Avalanche Hunters / Монтгомери Отуотер; Пер.с англ. Г. Н. Голубева; Под. ред. Г. К. Тушинского. — Изд. 2-е, стер.. — М.: Мир, 1980. — 256 с.